

Case Report

Management of Rhesus Isoimmunized Pregnant Woman in Low Resource Setting: A Case Report

Isah AD¹, Agida TE², Nongo BH³, Mohammed BR⁴, Jibril AO⁵, Itanyi UD⁶.

^{1,2,3,4} Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Abuja, ⁵ Department of Pediatrics, University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Abuja, ⁶ Department of Radiology, University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Abuja.

ABSTRACT

Rh isoimmunization of pregnant mothers may be responsible for varying severity of anaemia in fetuses and newborns. Usually, it is in the second or subsequent pregnancies that the fetus is affected. Management of this patient in a low resource setting posed serious challenges as various interventions levels. A 28-year-old G6P5+0 1alive at 17weeks of gestation, in her six pregnancy who had developed Anti-D antibodies after her first pregnancy. pregnancy was unbooked, carried to term and had spontaneous vaginal delivery at home to a live female neonate. She was unaware of her blood group and Rhesus typing and did not received Anti-D immunoglobulin. Subsequently, she had recurrent intrauterine stillbirth and early neonatal death. Current pregnancy was carried to 31weeks of gestation when it was noticed the fetus had severe anaemia following evaluation with middle cerebral artery-peak systolic velocity and had Caesarean section. The neonate had exchange blood transfusion and phototherapy following delivery. Close fetal monitoring with middle cerebral artery- peak systolic velocity and timely delivery can lead to a favorable outcome in low resource setting.

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***Correspondence:**
Isah AD, Department of
Obstetrics and Gynecology,
University of Abuja Teaching
Hospital, Abuja.
Tel: +234
Email: denisanthonysisah@yahoo.
com

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INTRODUCTION

The human red blood cell membrane is complex and contains a number of clinically relevant blood group antigens, the most relevant being the ABO and the Rhesus blood group antigens. This blood group systems can result in haemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn and hemolytic transfusion reaction. The D antigen is the most immunogenic and most clinically relevant of the Rhesus antigens. Phenotypic distribution of Rh(D) in Nigeria varies from one part of the country to the other. The overall average prevalence of Rhesus negativity is 5.1%. The distribution of Rh(D) in Nigeria is in agreement with others parts of the world¹⁻⁸. In Nigeria and other developing countries, the low

prevalence of Rhesus negativity is a blessing in disguise because following potentially sensitizing events that gives raise to fetomaternal hemorrhage during the course of pregnancy can lead to Rh incompatibility and hemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn. The use of routine antenatal anti-D prophylaxis and other anti-D hemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn related prevention strategies are not being implemented. There are several challenges associated with the management of Rhesus negative pregnancies, pregnancies associated with clinically significant alloantibodies, implementation of policy on routine antenatal anti-D prophylaxis, management of Rhesus negative women that require termination of pregnancy, provision of antigen negative blood for certain patient groups and the management of pregnant and non-pregnant patients with clinically significant alloantibodies.

Routine antenatal anti-D prophylaxis is a recommended treatment option for all Rhesus D negative pregnant women who are not known to be sensitized previously to the RhD antigen.

CASE REPORT

Mrs I.N a 28-year-old booked G₆P⁵⁺⁰ (1 alive) Rhesus Negative mother whose last menstrual period was 28-07-20. She is a stylist with secondary level of education, married to a 32-year-old Civil Servant in a monogamous setting.

She was first seen at the booking clinic on 23-11-20 at estimated gestational age of 17 weeks and history of recurrent intrauterine fetal dead and early neonatal death after her first delivery and having had 2 previous caesarean sections. At booking, Indirect Coombs test and routine antenatal investigations including Obstetric ultrasound, were done. The Indirect Coombs test was Positive with titre of >4096. Her Packed cell volume was 32%, Blood group was O Negative, Genotype was AS, Human Immunodeficiency virus screening, Hepatitis B & C

were Negative. Venereal Research disease laboratory test was Non-reactive. Urinalysis was normal. Obstetric ultrasound revealed a singleton intrauterine fetus with good cardiac activity, BPD-4.37cm, FL-2.91cm, estimated gestational age of 19 weeks and estimated date of delivery was 28-04-2021 with a low-lying placenta. The gestational age on ultrasound correlates with gestational age from her last menstrual period.

She was given 4-weekly appointment until she was 28 weeks when she was admitted into maternity ward for close fetal surveillance. She kept fetal kick charts, had weekly Doppler Obstetric ultrasound with emphasis on middle cerebral artery Peak systolic volume to detect features of fetal anaemia and guide timely intervention. The neonatologists were informed with necessary preparations made. She remained stable on admission, the fetal kick charts were adequate and had her 3 doses of intermittent preventive anti malaria drugs.. Initial Doppler middle cerebral artery (MCA) Peak Systolic velocity (PSV) Multiple of median (MOM) was normal.

Serial Doppler MCA PSV revealed increase in both MOM and PSV from 0.82 to 0.9 and 40.3cm/s to 50.9cm/s when compared to the gestational age respectively. This was suggestive of cerebral sparing. This subsequently rose to 1.5 and 1.8 MOM and PSV increasing to 68cm/s and 80.1cm/s respectively and subsequent Ultrasound scan done did not showed any features of hydrops. She was counseled on findings and need to effect delivery. A written informed consent was obtained and patient was booked for caesarean section. She had Emergency Caesarean Section with right cystectomy on the 31st day on admission.

Intra-operative findings were healed Pfannenstiel scar, moderate pelvic adhesions, a live male neonate Apgar scores 6¹ and 8⁵. Birth weight was 1.6kg. A right ovarian cyst measuring about 12cm x 10cm. Estimated blood loss was 600mls. Cord blood was sent for packed cell volume, blood grouping and

serum bilirubin.

The baby was immediately admitted into the special baby care unit with findings of severe pallor, respiratory distress with respiratory rate of 40 cycles per minute. Oxygen saturation in room air was 74%. The baby was managed for severe anaemia 2^o to Rhesus Isoimmunization. Urgent packed cell volume was 16%, Blood group was O positive. The baby was commenced on continuous positive airway pressure, intranasal oxygen, had top up transfusion with 10mls of compatible blood and 1 session of single volume exchange blood transfusion of 103mls over one hour. Baby was commenced on prophylactic phototherapy and add additional blood transfusion on 2 occasions, 6 days apart following drop in packed cell volume from 40% following the exchange blood transfusion to 25% and then 32%. Intravenous antibiotics, intravenous fluid with Dextrose made up to 7.5%, Caffeine citrate and Vitamin K. Intravenous Sodium bicarbonate commenced due to declining SPO2 to 89% despite being on CPAP. Trophic feeding was commenced on the 5th day of life and well tolerated. He was treated for malaria using intravenous Artesunate. Subcutaneous erythropoietin, intravenous Dexamethasone.

Respiratory distress subsided and weaned off oxygen on the 13th day on admission. He received intravenous albumin and commenced on Kangaroo Mother Care. On 22nd day on admission, baby was noticed to have a drop in SPO2 from 93% to 83%, in respiratory distress and packed cell volume dropped from 48% to 35%. He was managed for nosocomial infection with background anaemia. He was recommenced on intranasal oxygen, intravenous antibiotics and had the 3rd session of blood transfusion. On 25th day on admission, clinical condition had improved, tolerating expressed breast milk and weaned off intranasal oxygen. Mother recommenced Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC). He was discharged home on the 28th day on admission, with a post-transfusion packed cell

Figure 1: Normal MCA-PSV

Figure 2: MCA-PSV 1.7MOM

Figure 3: MCA-PSV 1.8MOM

volume of 35%. He continued on oral antibiotics and to be followed up in Paediatric out-patient clinic. The mother was to be followed-up in Post-natal clinic.

DISCUSSION

Rhesus isoimmunization is an important clinical entity which is responsible for fetal anaemia and hydrops fetalis, and if not treated, it can result in intrauterine fetal demise. Rh isoimmunization can be prevented with simple measures and treated if recognized in time thereby preventing debilitating consequences. Following potentially sensitizing events; abdominal trauma, abortion or termination of pregnancy, antepartum hemorrhage (APH), amniocentesis, chorionic villus sampling, external cephalic version (ECV) and miscarriages during pregnancy, small amounts of fetal blood can enter into the maternal circulation. The Rh-D antigen on fetal cells, which is circulating in maternal blood, is recognized by maternal reticuloendothelial system (RES) as foreign antigen. The RES responds with the formation of IgM antibodies against Rh-D antigen in small amount (initial response). These antibodies can be detected in the blood of this individual within few weeks' time. When there is second time exposure to this foreign antigen (during second pregnancy with an Rh-D positive pregnancy), the previously primed memory B cells respond more strongly with the formation of IgG antibodies. This initial response could be prevented if the fetal RBCs entering the maternal circulation are removed before they are detected by the maternal RES. This can be achieved by giving anti-D immunoglobulins to the mother so as to counteract appropriately for the FMH.

Once sensitization has occurred it is irreversible. In our case her first pregnancy was unbooked and she is not aware of her blood group and Rhesus typing. She Carried the pregnancy to term and had spontaneous vaginal delivery at home. No anti-D immunoglobulin was given. This served as the factor responsible for

the sensitization. In the subsequent pregnancies, she had stillbirth and early neonatal death due to Rhesus isoimmunization.

The risk of RhD alloimmunization during or immediately after a first pregnancy is about 1.5%. Administration of anti-D at 28 weeks and 34 weeks gestation to women in their first pregnancy can reduce this risk to about 0.2% without, to date, any adverse effects⁹. Although such a policy is unlikely to confer benefit or improve outcome in the present pregnancy, fewer women will have Rhesus D antibodies in their next pregnancy. The policy to give anti-D immunoglobulin at 28 and 34 weeks of gestation will need to consider the costs of prophylaxis against the costs of care for women who become sensitized and their affected infants, and local adequacy of supply of anti-D gammaglobulin⁹. However, routine administration of anti-D immunoglobulin in the third trimester as prophylaxis against small amounts of fetomaternal haemorrhage that can occur in the absence of observable sensitizing events. This is known as routine antenatal anti-D prophylaxis. The use of anti-D immunoglobulin for routine antenatal anti-D prophylaxis is in addition to the administration of anti-D immunoglobulin following potentially sensitizing events, and its use in either indication is not affected by prior use in the other¹⁰.

This lady presented at 17weeks gestation with bad Obstetrics history. After investigation, her Rhesus typing came out to be O negative and indirect Coomb's test was positive. Management of such case of Rhesus isoimmunization especially in developing countries are face with lack of facility to assay the antibody titre and expertise in amniocentesis and intrauterine transfusion. This patient was managed with Ultrasound scan using the middle cerebral artery-peak systolic velocity (MCA-PSV) as inpatient from 26weeks of gestation. At 31weeks of gestation, it was noticed MCA-PSV started rising and there was evidence of fetal anaemia. At that point she

had Caeserean section and the baby was adequately managed in special baby care unit.

This case demonstrates that a favourable outcome is possible in cases of Rhesus antibodies if proper monitoring is done and timely delivery.

CONCLUSION

Where skills are lacking in amniocentesis and intrauterine transfusion, the role of middle cerebral artery-peak systolic velocity using Ultrasound scan is equally important in the monitoring of patient with Rhesus isoimmunization

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